

MECHANICAL EVALUATION OF NEW FIBER METAL LAMINATES MADE BY THE VARTM PROCESS

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SUMMARY

This paper investigates the tensile and fatigue properties of a newly developed fiber metal laminate (FML) consisting of glass fiber reinforced epoxy and 2024-T3 aluminum alloy. Due to the manufacturing using the vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) method, the FML is cheaper than the comparable GLARE 3. However, the metal sheets need to be perforated in order for the laminate to infiltrate and these holes act as crack initiators. Tension and fatigue test results are reported for two different thickness VARTM FMLs with and without holes in the aluminum alloy and compared to mechanical property predictions as well as to GLARE 3 data.

Keywords: vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM), fiber metal laminate (FML), hybrid composites, fatigue, tensile behavior, GLARE 3, classic laminate theory (CLT), rule of mixtures (ROM), non-linear behavior

1. INTRODUCTION

Fiber metal laminates (FMLs) are advanced aerospace materials. They consist of multiple thin layers of metal alternately bonded to thin layers of fiber-reinforced polymers. FMLs combine the best properties of the metal and the composite.

The development of fiber metal laminates, or hybrid composite laminates, started back in 1967 when Kaufman [1] showed that a laminate of multiple adhesively bonded aluminum plies has about twice the fracture toughness of a single aluminum specimen of the same overall dimensions. In 1978, Johnson et al. [2] showed that the crack growth resistance and fatigue life in aluminum laminate is greatly enhanced compared to monolithic aluminum. In 1983, Johnson [3] showed that the improvement of damage tolerance was also true for laminated titanium versus monolithic titanium. Voegesang et al. at the Technische Universiteit Delft together with ALCOA developed the first fiber metal composite consisting of aluminum sheets and aramid fiber reinforced plies in the 1980s [4]. This first hybrid metal laminate is known as ARALL (Aramid Reinforced ALuminum Laminate). ARALL showed the damage tolerance and fracture toughness known from the metal laminates together with the strength and crack growth resistance brought in by the fibers. GLARE (GLASS REinforced fiber metal laminate), using R and S2 glass fibers, was then introduced in 1991 [5], due to the good compressive properties of glass. These compressive properties lead to a better loading

flexibility of GLARE compared to ARALL since aramid fibers show a very poor behavior under compressive loading [6].

FMLs are known to be lightweight, have good fatigue properties and impact resistance, high specific static properties; they are flame and corrosion resistant and have good blunt notch strength [7], [8]. These properties make FMLs, like GLARE, a very attractive material for aerospace applications. Due to the manufacturing of prepreg and in an autoclave, GLARE is expensive to produce and dimensional restrictions apply. The NASA Langley Research Center subsequently developed a material similar in design to GLARE, which is manufactured using dry fibers and vacuum assisted resin transfer molding. The material will therefore be referred to as VARTM FML. VARTM FML has the advantage of being cheaper in manufacturing and produced panels are not dimensionally limited by the size of the autoclave. However, in contrast to the aluminum alloy foils in GLARE the foils in medium sized to larger panels of VARTM FML need to be perforated in order for the resin to infiltrate. This clearly is a disadvantage since the holes (0.016" diameter) in the metal foils act as crack initiators.

The presented work reports experimental results that were gained in tensile tests and tension-tension fatigue tests. The experimental data is compared to the modeled characteristics such as the Young's modulus, the yield strength and the ultimate tensile strength. Additionally, the tensile and fatigue data is compared to GLARE 3 – since both, the VARTM FML in this research as well as GLARE 3 are comprised of each 50% 0° and 90° fibers. Additionally, the results are compared to some specimens without holes produced with the VARTM method.

2. MANUFACTURING AND SPECIMEN FEATURES

In the typical VARTM process, the dry layers are stacked on the one-sided tooling, see Figure 1. The layup is then covered by a flexible sheet or liner to seal the perform before the air is evacuated using a vacuum pump. A matrix resin from an external reservoir is introduced to the component due to the pressure difference between the preform under vacuum and the resin reservoir. A resin distribution medium put on the top and bottom of the dry layup facilitates the flow in the lengthwise direction of the part which also accelerates the through thickness flow. In the manufacturing of the tested specimens, the flow medium was put on top and underneath the fiber preform unlike shown in the drawing. The VARTM FML plates were cured for 5 hours at 125°F followed by 6 hours at 165°F. In order to allow complete impregnation and to reduce the formation of voids, the resin must be of a very low injection viscosity.

Fig.1: Schematic of the VARTM process; courtesy of NASA Langley Research Center

As stated above, the research was conducted on 2024-T3 aluminum alloy / fiberglass FMLs. The composite in the FLM is a woven fiberglass mat consisting of 0° and 90° fibers in equal shares. The resin SC-85 was used. In earlier experiments performed in the same lab, an average elastic modulus E_{11} of 4050 ksi was experimentally measured for the composite part of the FML.

All specimens consist of five Al alloy layers and four composite layers. Each composite layer exists of one single woven fabric layer. The textile like woven structure that can be observed on the surface of the specimens is patterned resin that reproduces the weave of the resin distribution medium that has been removed after curing. The green color arises from the pretreatment of the aluminum.

Two different Al alloy foil thicknesses have been used to manufacture the specimens: 0.31mm or 0.012" (thin specimens) and respectively 0.34mm or 0.015" (thick specimens). The overall rectangular specimen dimensions are: 8" and respectively 7.5" in length for the thin and respectively thick specimens, 1" in width, and 0.1" (thin specimens) and respectively 0.119" (thick specimens) in specimen thickness. The different overall thicknesses are due to the different Al foil thicknesses; the composite thickness in both designs is the same.

The plate of thick specimens was produced such that half the plate had holes drilled in the aluminum layers through which the resin could enter the inner glassfiber layers and half the plate did not contain holes. This way, the resin entered through the holes and propagated inside until the whole panel was infiltrated. Six specimens with holes and six specimens without holes were cut from this plate.

Clamping the specimen without tabs resulted in the specimen slipping out of the grips at the appropriate clamping pressure. Increasing the clamping pressure resulted in a failure at the grip area, so all specimens were tabbed with 2" long, 1" wide and 0.015" thick brass.

3. MODELING

Different models have been developed to predict the mechanical properties of GLARE laminates. Two established models were used to predict the VARTM FML properties. These models were the classical laminate theory (CLT) and the rule of mixtures (ROM) as used by Wu et al. [9] and De Vries et al. [10].

Table 1: Modeled mechanical properties of the VARTM FML

property	thin		thick	
	CLT	ROM	CLT	ROM
$E_{11}^{lam} = E_{22}^{lam}$ [ksi]	7982.7	7980	8180.7	8178.2
$\sigma_{y,lam}$ [ksi]	-	37.6	-	38.6
σ_{lam}^{ult}	-	74	-	73.7

Table 2: Mechanical properties of the aluminum alloy and composite layers of both the thin and the thick VARTM FML specimens

E [ksi]	h [in]	σ_y [ksi]	σ^{ult} [ksi]	ν [-]
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Al	comp	Al	FML total	Al	comp	Al	comp	Al	comp
10600	4050	0.012	0.1	50	-	70	80	0.33	0.286
10600	4050	0.015	0.119	50	-	70	80	0.33	0.286

4. TENSILE BEHAVIOR

A servohydraulic test frame equipped with PC-based test control and data acquisition systems was used to perform the tensile and fatigue testing for this research project. The MTS test frame was equipped with hydraulic wedge grips with a force capacity of 100kN / 22kip and a load cell with a capacity of 10 metric tons. An MTS extensometer model 632.31-21 was used to collect the data.

A variety of research, e.g. [9], [11] - [13], has shown that the tensile stress-strain curve of FMLs is highly nonlinear due to the plasticity of the metal sheets. The deviation from Hooke's law is particularly high in the case of glassfiber / aluminum FMLs, since the high strain-to-failure of the glass fibers (about 3% for the woven fabric used for the VARTM FML, [14]) allows for a larger portion of the metal nonlinearity being displayed. As a result, the tensile strength and the elongation to break of an aluminum/glassfiber FML can be 50 - 100% respectively an order of a magnitude higher than the corresponding values at yield strength, [15].

In a first linear part of the stress strain curve, both metal and composite layers are loaded elastically. Once the metal starts yielding, the stress-strain-curve gets into a transition area, where it is no longer linear. Since the composite is still reinforcing the laminate, the stress-strain relation becomes linear again as the glass fiber composite can be assumed to be linear elastic until fracture [13]. It can be generally said that in the tensile mode, the Al yields but does not fail until the composite layers have failed.

Fig.3: σ - ϵ curves of the thin specimens 4, 6, and 13 (black) and the thick specimens 1 and 7 (red and blue). The notion "90 deg" states that the specimen was cut out of the plate 90° compared to the other specimens

A total of five tensile tests were performed; three with thin specimens and each one with the thick specimens with and without holes. The resulting stress-strain curves are shown

in Figure 3 and the corresponding values for yield strength σ_y , ultimate tensile strength σ^{ult} , and maximum elongation ϵ_f are displayed in Table 3.

Table 3: Mechanical properties of the tensile specimens in comparison with the modeled properties

specimen #	E [ksi]			σ_y [ksi]		σ^{ult} [ksi]		ϵ_f [%]
	experiment	ROM	CLT	exp.	ROM	exp.	ROM	exp.
thin	4	8410		39.1		69.1		2.9
	6	7800	7980	38.6	37.6	65.3	74	2.6
	13	8070	7982.7	37.8		71.1		2.9
	average	8093.3		38.5		68.5		2.8
thick	1	7800		37.6		62.5		2.7
	7	8115	8178.2	36.9	38.6	67.9	73.7	3.2
	average	8065	8180.7	37.25		65.2		2.95

The predicted Young's modulus of the thin samples is only 1.5% smaller than the average measured value. For the thick specimens, the deviation is -1.4% and thus both modeled values match very well with the experimentally derived results.

The yield strength of the VARTM FML was predicted based on the 0.2% offset value of the 2024-T3 aluminum alloy, so the results are compared to 0.2% offset experimental values. The average yield strength was determined to be 38.5ksi for the thin samples and 37.25ksi for the thick samples. These values deviate from the predicted results of 37.6ksi for the thin and 38.6ksi for the thick specimens by only 2% for the thin and -3.5% for the thick samples respectively.

The ultimate tensile strength was modeled as 74ksi for the thin specimens and the experiments revealed values averaging 68.5ksi. This is a deviation of -7.5% and thus not as good as the prediction for the yield strength. The same is true for the thick samples, where the average experimentally derived value of 65.2ksi is 11.5% lower than the modeled ultimate tensile strength of 73.3ksi. One reason for this could be the assumption of the ROM that the failure of all FML components happens simultaneously, which proves generally not true [16].

The conclusion that can be drawn is that the predictions yielded with the rule of mixtures are quite accurate for the Young's modulus and the yield strength, but not as good for the ultimate tensile strength. Van Roijen reports comparable results in [16].

Fig.4: Typical tensile crack characteristic

All tensile cracks have common characteristics like a random crack pattern, gray discolored surface areas that indicate plastic deformation which can also be seen at the edge of the specimens, and fiber pullout at the crack, see Figure 4. The crack paths of the specimens go through holes and the cracks in the different metal layers are vertically aligned through the thickness. This is the result of the laminate layup: due to the drilling through the whole stack of metal plates at once, the aluminum alloy layers and the glass fiber mats are stacked up so that the holes are more or less on top of each other in the different layers.

5. FATIGUE BEHAVIOR

The fatigue properties of the VARTM FML were investigated in cyclic tests at room temperature. All VARTM fatigue tests were performed at a stress ratio $R = 0.1$ and at a frequency of 10Hz. The thin specimens were fatigued at different maximum stresses in order to create a rough SN-curve, whereas the thick specimens were too little in number to result in even a rough SN-curve. Therefore, the two different kinds of thick specimens — with and without holes — were all fatigued at the same maximum stress in order to compare them with each other and the thin specimens.

5.1 Crack Initiation

Fatigue cracks initiate in the aluminum layers since the fiberglass layers are comparatively insensitive to cyclic loading. The fatigue initiation is essentially the same as in monolithic aluminum. However, as a result of the high modulus of the aluminum and the low modulus of the glass fiber composite of the VARTM FML and GLARE, the actual stresses in the aluminum layers are higher than in the composite layers and higher than the applied laminate stresses. These stresses can be calculated using the classic lamination theory¹. The high stress in the aluminum results in a shorter crack initiation life of glass fiber aluminum laminates compared to monolithic aluminum at the same applied stress [17].

5.2 Crack Propagation

In contrast to the crack initiation life, the crack propagation life of glass fiber aluminum laminates is longer than in monolithic aluminum due to crack closure mechanisms by intact fibers over the fatigue crack. This effect is known as fiber bridging. While fatigue cracks propagate through the aluminum layers, the intact fibers carry much of the load over the crack in the aluminum and thereby decelerate crack opening. Fiber bridging reduces the stress intensity at the crack tip in the Al layers and therefore reduces the crack propagation rate considerably [18]. The balance between delamination length, crack opening and bridging stress during crack propagation leads to approximately constant crack growth rates, which, according to Young et al. [5], for GLARE leads to a fatigue life that is 10 to 100 times higher than the fatigue life of the aluminum alloy alone.

Apart from fatigue crack growth in the aluminum layers, delamination at the interfaces between the aluminum and the fiber layers takes place. Delamination is induced by shear stresses, that result from the fiber bridging; i.e. the load transfer from the

¹ Specimen strain: $\varepsilon = \varepsilon_C = \varepsilon_{Al} = \sigma_{Al} E_{Al} = \sigma_C E_C$ so if $E_{Al} > E_C$ then $\sigma_{Al} > \sigma_C$. Also, the coefficients of thermal expansion in aluminum and the composite layer are different from each other ($\alpha_{Al} > \alpha_C$), leading to tensile residual stresses in the aluminum layers and compressive residual stresses in the composite.

aluminum layer to the composite layer [19].

Generally, it can be said that in fatigue, the aluminum fails first by growing fatigue cracks and the composite fails only once it can no longer support the increasing load.

5.3 Experiments

In fatigue, all specimens were tested at a stress ratio $R = 0.1$ and a frequency of 10Hz. The fatigue experiments of the thin specimens were aimed at the creation of a rough S-N curve. Two details were given special attention:

First the high cycle fatigue, since there were not enough specimens to create an accurate entire SN curve. To do this, many specimens would be needed, since results tend to be scattered a lot in fatigue tests. As only 16 specimens were available from the first manufactured plate for all the tensile and fatigue tests, and low cycle fatigue is usually not of interest in aerospace applications, more specimens were used to find the stress level at which the specimens would withstand one million cycles or start developing cracks.

Second, fatiguing the thin specimens at various stress levels between 40% and 90% yield strength gave a rough idea of the SN curve for the thin specimens. However, the intention was also to compare the results to the two different kinds of thick specimens of which much less were available, so not even a rough estimation of a SN curve could be produced with these specimens. Therefore, it seemed reasonable to fatigue multiple specimens at the same stress level of 27ksi and to compare the specimens accordingly. The stress level represents the overall stress for the whole specimen, so the stress in the Al plies is different in the thin and respectively thick specimens.

Table 4 gives an overview of all fatigued VARTM FML specimens including the maximum stress and number of cycles to failure, where failure is defined as when the specimen was pulled into two pieces. Figure 5 shows the same values in a SN graph, comparing it to a single GLARE 3 value that was gained in the same lab during a senior design project. Even though it is not known how realistic this value is, it compares very well to the VARTM FML values.

Comparing the overall fatigue life of the thick specimens to the thin specimens, it is obvious that first, the specimens without holes clearly have the longest fatigue life. The examination of crack growth in the fatigue specimens shows that the holes serve as crack initiators due to the stress concentration around the hole. Second, the thin specimens with holes have a longer fatigue life than the thick specimens with holes. As stated earlier, the thin specimens are different from the thick specimens only as for the thickness of the metal foil. The composite layers are the same thickness in both the thin and the thick specimens. This means that the thin specimens have a higher composite volume fraction compared to the thick specimens. In [23] the same effect was observed, where crack resistance curves indicate that an increase in composite volume fraction improves the fatigue life. Cortes and Cantwell state that delamination is more likely to happen in laminates with thick fiber-reinforced composite layers than in thin composite layer FMLs. This said it is to point out that even though small delaminations have positive effects on the crack propagation, large delaminations result in a reduction of the bridging stress and therefore an increase in crack opening.

Fig. 5: SN curve based on the maximum overall stress at R=0.1; the arrows indicate that the tests have been stopped after 1,000,000 cycles before failure of the specimen

Please note that the SN data in Figure 5 is representing the general fatigue behavior of the VARTM FML but does by no means reflect a definitive SN curve. The figures do show the qualitative performance of the material and make it possible to compare the different specimen types, but too few specimens were tested to assemble an SN curve for the VARTM FML.

The only sample that withstood 1,000,000 cycles without any apparent crack growth is the sample that was cycled at about 40% of the yield strength or 15ksi maximum load. The samples that were fatigued at 18ksi show one to three fatigue cracks, but none of them had grown through the entire width of the specimen. As expected, it is found that the higher the maximum applied load is, the more fatigue cracks develop.

Table 4: Fatigue test overview; all tests were performed at R=0.1 and 10Hz. * means test was stopped after 1,000,000 cycles before specimen failed

specimen #	max. stress [ksi]	cycles to failure [-]
thin VARTM specimens with holes		
1	18	*
2	18	*
3	21	706,726
5	27	199,510
7	24	380,698
8	20	98,170
9	15	*
10	21	549,673
11	27	238,154
12	18	*
15	27	166,384
16	27	162,184
thick VARTM specimens with holes		
2	27	62,938

3		82,811
4		77,473
5		199,510
6		47,515
	average	94,949.4
	standard deviation	54,141.3
thick VARTM specimens without holes		
8		118,162
9		163,820
10	27	334,749
11		298,422
12		277,577
	average	238,546
	standard deviation	82,993.8

All fatigue tests performed on specimens with holes show obvious similarities in the crack characteristics, see Figure 6. The fatigue cracks initiate at holes in a very straight manner perpendicular to the load axis. Some layers show areas in which an existing straight fatigue crack changed into a tensile crack with random pattern and plastic deformation. Especially specimens that were tested at low max. stresses show multiple cracks in the Al layers, often through the entire specimen width. These cracks grew simultaneously and show large areas of delamination that resulted from fiber bridging.

Some fatigue specimens show single layers that failed in a tensile mode rather than in a fatigue mode. These layers seem to have failed spontaneously in a once all or most other layers had failed in fatigue. The fatigue crack that grew in the neighboring layer leads to delamination in the vicinity of the crack which helps fiber bridging to take place. So more load is carried by the layer adjacent to the one with the fatigue crack. Due to the delaminated area, the stress concentration in the intact layer is highest at the edge of the delamination, where the load is transferred through. In this area of high stress concentration, the layer fails once the increasing load cannot be carried anymore.

Even though the thick and the thin specimens have many commonalities, the thick specimens with holes generally failed at a shorter fatigue life than the thin specimens. The straight fatigue cracks are significantly smaller than in the thin specimens as the crack schematics show and a bigger percentage of the crack region is plastically deformed, showing signs of a spontaneous failure.

Fig. 6: Typical fatigue crack characteristics in specimens with holes

As for the thick specimens without holes, none shows additional cracks other than the cracks that present the final failure. The cracks generally initiated at the edge of the specimens. Since no holes serve as crack initiation sites, the specimens fatigue initiation is considerably longer than for the specimens with holes. Assuming that the crack propagation time is the same, this explains why the fatigue life of these specimens is significantly longer than compared to the thick specimens with holes. Another difference compared to the specimens with holes is that the different metal layers fail with larger distances between each other regarding the lengthwise direction, see Figure 7. However, crack characteristics such as the straightness of the cracks and the transition of fatigue cracks into tensile cracks are as in the specimens with holes.

Fig. 7: Typical fatigue crack characteristics in specimens without holes

In all fatigue specimens, first fatigue cracks have been observed to appear in the outer layers, where fiber bridging can only occur on one side of the aluminum alloy layer, which means that the free surface is less constrained. This effect has been previously observed in [20] - [22].

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